

LIMITED-USE VOCABULARY IN LITERARY TEXTS
Zilola Khayrullo kizi Khaliljonova

Fergana State University

Faculty of Philology and Language Teaching

(Uzbek Language) 1st-year student:

M.Gaziyeva

Scientific advisor:

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the concept of the lexeme, its essence as a unit expressing lexical meaning, and its place in the language system. It also analyzes types of lexemes according to their scope of usage, particularly limited vocabulary—archaisms, historicisms, dialectisms, professionalisms, and vulgarisms. Their functions in literary texts—such as creating imagery, reflecting historical and local settings, and ensuring stylistic diversity—are illustrated with examples.

A **lexeme** (Greek: *lexis* — word, expression) is a lexical unit of language structure that expresses meaning. The meaning conveyed by a lexeme arises in human consciousness by linking a certain sound complex to an objective reality. Such units exist in both words and phrases. The terms *glosseme* and *lexical morpheme* are also used in this regard. For example, the lexeme *house* means “a building where a person lives,” while *to run* means “to move quickly from one place to another.” Therefore, lexemes are studied not only semantically but also phonetically and grammatically.

According to their scope of usage, vocabulary can be divided into **unrestricted** and **restricted**. This classification mainly applies to nouns, adjectives, adverbs, and verbs. Numerals, pronouns, conjunctions, particles, postpositions, and interjections generally do not exhibit restricted usage. Unrestricted lexical units are used widely by speakers regardless of region, dialect, or profession.

In literary texts, **restricted vocabulary** refers to words specific to a certain region (dialect), profession, or social group, unlike general language. These words enhance imagery, expressiveness, and locality. They serve to individualize characters’ speech, depict historical or local settings, and create stylistic richness.

If a word has an archaic tone in modern usage, it is called an **archaism**. Archaisms are mainly used in literary texts to depict past events and create a historical atmosphere. For example, the word *cholvor* (trousers) is now replaced by *shim*, making it an archaic lexical item. This shows that archaisms still have meaning today but differ in form.

A **historicism** refers to an outdated lexical unit used to denote objects or phenomena that no longer exist. For example, *qalapoy afzali* belongs to this category because such

footwear is no longer used today. Unlike archaisms, historicisms do not have modern equivalents.

Another type of restricted vocabulary is **dialectal lexicon**. These words are specific to people living in a particular region. In literary texts, dialectisms help show a character's origin and local environment, adding authenticity and a folk flavor.

Professional vocabulary (professionalisms) includes terms related to specific occupations or fields such as production, science, or art. For instance, *manipulyatsionnaya* is widely used in the medical field but not commonly understood by the general public.

Another type widely used in literary texts is **vulgarisms**. These are words used in a rude or insulting sense. They are not considered part of the standard literary language and are inappropriate in formal speech. However, in literary works, they are used to enhance stylistic expressiveness and realism.

Conclusion. The lexeme is the fundamental lexical unit of language and plays a key role in expressing reality. It is a complex unit connected not only with meaning but also with phonetic and grammatical aspects. Lexemes vary according to their scope of usage, and limited vocabulary—such as archaisms, historicisms, dialectisms, professionalisms, and vulgarisms—reflects the historical, regional, and social features of a language. In literary texts, these lexical units serve as important tools for creating imagery, accurately depicting settings, and ensuring stylistic diversity..